

Validated Task Collection

This appendix contains the final task collection after two rounds of adjustments (based on the survey results and interview results).

1. Validated task collection variables

V1C1

Task	<p>Given the following code, what is the output? Provide the answer in a free text field.</p> <pre>1 a = 200 2 a = 20 3 print(a)</pre>
Correct answer	20
Expected Error(s)	<p>1) output: 120 → Values assigned to the variable will sum up instead of remembering only one, last assigned value.</p> <p>2) output: a → Symbolic name of the variable will print out, instead of the value of the variable.</p> <p>3) output: 100 → Variable remembers only the initial value.</p>

V2C1

Task	<p>Given the following code, what is the output? Provide the answer in a free text field.</p> <pre>1 a = 100 2 a = 20 3 print('a')</pre>
Correct answer	a
Expected Error(s)	<p>1) output: 120 → Values assigned to the variable will sum up instead of remembering only one, last assigned value.</p> <p>2) output: 20 → Value of the variable will be printed, instead of the symbolic name.</p> <p>3) output: 100 → Variable remembers only the initial value.</p>

V3C1

Task	<p>Given the following code, what is the output? Provide the answer in a free text field.</p> <pre> 1 a = 100 2 a = a+1 3 print(a) </pre>
Correct answer	101
Expected Error(s)	<p>output: a+1 →Variable value is a string rather than its previous incremented value/ variable holds an unevaluated expression instead of being incremented; known misconception about equal sign which students often replace with the math equation.</p>

V4C1

Task	<p>Given the following code, what is the output? Provide the answer in a free text field.</p> <pre> 1 a = 100 2 b = a 3 print (a,b) </pre>
Correct answer	100 100
Expected Error(s)	<p>output: a b →Not assigning the variable value to another variable.</p>

V5C1

Task	<p>Given the following code, what is the output? Provide the answer in a free text field.</p> <pre> 1 a = 100 2 b = 20 3 a = 20 4 print (a,b) </pre>
Correct answer	20 20
Expected Error(s)	<p>output: 100 20 →Variable remembers the first value while ignoring the reassignment of the variable value.</p>

V1C2

Task	Write a piece of python code to display the age of Mara who is seven years old and Max who is 11 years old. Use variables to display the individual age and to calculate the sum of how old Mara and Max are together. Make use of the calculated sum and print it.
Correct answer	Different ways of implementation, e.g. <pre>age_mara = 7 age_max = 11 sum = age_mara + age_max print(sum)</pre>
Expected Error(s)	No 'meaningful' naming of variables

V2C2

Task	<p>Given the following code:</p> <pre>1 c = 1 2 3 def add(): 4 c = c+2 5 print(c) 6 7 add()</pre> <p>The program tries to print the variable called 'c' but it does not work and provides an error. Find the error(s) and correct the code by correcting the body of the function. Write the corrected code in the free text field.</p>
Correct answer	<p>Use the global keyword to modify the variable from inside the function:</p> <pre>c = 1 def add(): global c c = c+2 print(c) add()</pre>
Expected Error(s)	Scope error - the program tries to modify the global variable c from inside the function.
Comment	This task refers not only to variables, but also to functions.

Task	<p>Given the following code:</p> <pre> 1 def find_max(n1, n2) 2 num1 = n1 3 num2 = n2 4 5 if num1 > num2: 6 result = num1 7 elif num2 > num1: 8 result = num2 9 else: 10 result = num1 11 return result 12 find_max(34,77) 13 print(result) </pre> <p>The program tries to print the variable called 'result' but it does not work and provides an error. Find the error(s) and correct the code. Don't change the last line of the given code. Write the corrected code in the free text field.</p>
Correct answer	<p>The function itself needs to be assigned to a variable, then it can be printed:</p> <pre> def find_max(n1, n2) num1 = n1 num2 = n2 if num1 > num2: result = num1 elif num2 > num1: result = num2 else: result = num1 return result maxNum = find_max(34,77) print(maxNum) </pre>
Expected Error(s)	Scope error - the program tries to print the variable result created inside of the function.
Comment	This task refers not only to variables, but also to functions

VIC3

Task	Write a loop that sums the values 1 through "end", inclusive. "end" is a variable that we will define later. So For example, if we define "end" to be 6, your code should print out the result "21" (which is 1+2+3+4+5+6). Do not include input statements and do not define "end" to a specific value. We will do this later.
Correct answer	Multiple implementations, e.g.: <pre>sum = 0 i = 0 while i <= end: sum += 1 i +=1 print(sum)</pre>
Expected Error(s)	Multiple errors, e.g.: not including the value of end by adding the condition as while i < end; order of statements within loop, initialization of variables, parameters to functions and return codes

2. Validated task collection loops

L1C1

Task	Print I as long as I is less than 6: <pre>1 i = 1 2 <input type="text"/> i < 6: 3 print(i) 4 i +=1</pre> Fill in the gap
Correct answer	while
Expected Error(s)	Usage of if statement instead of a while loop.

L2C1

Task	Loop through the items in the fruits list: <pre>1 fruits = ['apple', 'banana', 'cherry'] 2 <input type="text"/> x <input type="text"/> fruits: 3 print(x)</pre> Fill in the gaps
Correct answer	for in
Expected Error(s)	Usage of while instead of for, wrong syntax.

L3C1 (not anymore a 'class1' task, due to the adjustment this task is moved to 'class 2.)

Task	Translate the following code into a flowchart: <pre>1 i = 1 2 while i < 6: 3 if i == 3: 4 break 5 i += 1</pre>
Correct answer	Visual representation.
Expected Error(s)	No understanding of the break statement.

L4C1 (not anymore a 'class1' task, due to the adjustment this task is moved to 'class 2.)

Task	<p>Translate the following code into a flowchart:</p> <pre> 1 i = 1 2 while i < 6: 3 print(i) 4 i += 1 5 else: 6 print('i is no longer less than 6.')</pre>
Correct answer	Visual representation.
Expected Error(s)	No understanding of the else statement.

L5C1

Task	<pre> 1 num = 10 2 while num > 3: 3 num -= 1 4 print(num)</pre> <p>How many lines of code and what exactly does this loop print?</p>
Correct answer	<p>Seven lines of code:</p> <p>9 8 7 6 5 4 3</p>
Expected Error(s)	<p>1) off-by-one error and 2) misconception that a loop halts as soon as the loop condition is false, rather than first finishing the loop's body.</p>

L1C2

Task	<p>Convert the following into code that uses a while loop:</p> <pre> 2 4 6 8 10 Goodbye!</pre> <p>Write your code in the free text field</p>
Correct answer	<p>For example:</p> <pre> i=2 while i<12: print(i) i+=2 print("Goodbye!")</pre>
Expected Error(s)	Off-by-one error, wrong syntax of a while loop.

L2C2

Task	<p>Convert the following into code that uses a for loop:</p> <pre> 2 4 6 8 10 Goodbye!</pre> <p>Write your code in the free text field</p>
Correct answer	<p>For example:</p> <pre> for x in range (2,12,2): print(x) print ("Goodbye!")</pre>
Expected Error(s)	Off-by-one error, wrong syntax of a for loop.

L3C2

Task	<p>Given code:</p> <pre>1 def calculate_factorial(n): 2 result = 1 3 for i in range(1, n): 4 result = result * i 5 return result 6 7 print(calculate_factorial(5))</pre> <p>The function is designed to calculate the factorial of a given number n. If we run it for e.g. n=5, we would expect the output to be 120 (1*2*3*4*5 = 120). The code runs without any problem but gives an output of 24 instead of 120.</p> <p>Identify the error(s) and fix the code. Rewrite the code in the free text field.</p>
Correct answer	<p>Change the range for the for loop to include the number n itself (in line 3)</p> <pre>for I in range (1, n+1)</pre>
Expected Error(s)	<p>Off-by-one error.</p>

L4C2

Task	<p>We want to have the following output of a code snippet:</p> <pre>The count is: 1 The count is: 2 The count is: 3 The count is: 4 The count is: 5 That's it!</pre> <p>The given code snippet is:</p> <pre>1 count = 1 2 while (count < 5): 3 print('The count is:', count) 4 print("That's it!")</pre> <p>At the moment, the code is faulty and does not provide the requested output! Identify the error(s) and fix the code. Rewrite the code in the free text field.</p>
Correct answer	<p>1) Adjust the condition for the while loop (in line 2), e.g.:</p> <pre>while (count <= 5)</pre> <p>2) Add a counter (in line 4)</p> <pre>count +=1</pre>
Expected Error(s)	Infinite loop, off-by-one error.

L5C2

Task	<p>We want to print a rectangle pattern with 8 rows and 4 columns of stars. It should look like this:</p> <pre>* *</pre> <p>The given code snippet is:</p> <pre>1 for name in range(8): 2 for j in range(4): 3 print('*', end = ' ') 4 print()</pre> <p>At the moment, the code is faulty and does not provide the requested output! Identify the error(s) and fix the code. Rewrite the code in the free text field.</p>
Correct answer	<p>Intend the nested loop:</p> <pre>for name in range(8): for j in range(4): print('*', end='') print()</pre>
Expected Error(s)	Nested loops.

L2C3

Task	Write a program to display all prime numbers within a range Note: A Prime Number is a whole number greater than 1 whose only factors are 1 and itself.
Correct answer	Multiple implementations, e.g.: <pre>print("Prime numbers between", start, "and", end, "are:") for num in range(start, end + 1): if num > 1: for i in range(2, num): if (num % i) == 0: break else: print(num)</pre>
Expected Error(s)	Multiple errors, e.g.: Off-by-one errors, Syntax Errors, Misuse of "==" and "=" Infinite Loops; Misunderstanding of what a prime is, "slightly" faulty tests (e.g. check divisibility by 1).

3. Validated task collection functions

F1C1 (combined with F2C1)

Task	<p>Create a function named "my_func" to fill the gap in line 1 and call this function to fill the gap line 4:</p> <pre>1 <input type="text"/> 2 print("Hello from a function") 3 <input type="text"/> 4 <input type="text"/></pre>
Correct answer	<p>line 1: <code>def my_func():</code> line 4: <code>my_func()</code></p>
Expected Error(s)	<p>No understanding/ or confusion of how to define or call a function, syntax errors.</p>

F4C1 Subtask 1

Task	<p>What do the functions below return when you call them using <code>func_1()</code> and <code>func2()</code>?</p> <pre>1 def func_1(): 2 return 42 3 4 def func_2(): 5 print(42) -</pre>
Correct answer	<p><code>func_1()</code> returns nothing; <code>func_2()</code> returns 42</p>
Expected Error(s)	<p>No understanding of the return statement/ confusion with the print statement.</p>

F4C1 Subtask 2

Task	<p>What is the output generated in line 3 and line 7?</p> <pre> 1 def func_1(): 2 return 42 3 print(func_1()) 4 5 def func_2(): 6 print(42) 7 print(func_2()) </pre>
Correct answer	<p>output from line 3: 42</p> <p>output from line 7: 42 none</p>
Expected Error(s)	No understanding of the return statement/ confusion with the print statement.

F1C2

Task	<p>The function below takes two arguments - in our case 3 and 2 - adds five to both arguments and is supposed to output the new numbers. Hence the code below should return the following output: (7,8)</p> <p>Given code:</p> <pre> 1 def add5(a,b): 2 a=a+5, b=b+5 3 4 result = add5(3,2) 5 print(result) </pre> <p>At the moment, the code is faulty and does not provide the requested output! Identify the error(s) and fix the code. Modify the body of the function to provide the corrected output. Rewrite the code in the free text field.</p>
Correct answer	Change line 2 and add the return statement: return a+5, b+5
Expected Error(s)	No understanding of the return statement.

F2C2

Task	<p>The code below should return the following output: Hi, Ada Lovelace!</p> <p>Given code:</p> <pre> 1 def greeting(firstname, lastname): 2 def getFullName(): 3 return firstname + " " + lastname 4 print("Hi, " + "!") 5 6 greeting('Ada', 'Lovelace')</pre> <p>At the moment, the code is faulty and does not provide the requested output! Identify the error(s) and fix the code. Rewrite the code in the free text field.</p>
Correct answer	Change line 4 to call the inner function: <code>print("Hi, " + getFullName() + "!")</code>
Expected Error(s)	No understanding of the nesting of functions.

F3C2

Task	<p>The code below should return the following output: Emma 25</p> <p>Given code:</p> <pre> 1 def fun1(name, age=20): 2 print(name, age) 3 4 fun1('Emma')</pre> <p>At the moment, the code is faulty and does not provide the requested output! Identify the error(s) and fix the code. Rewrite the code in the free text field</p>
Correct answer	Add the second parameter in line 3: <code>fun1('Emma', 25)</code>
Expected Error(s)	No understanding of the parameter passing/ default parameter.

F4C2

Task	<p>The following code should sum up two values by using the function "add()". The code below should print the sum as an output, in our example it should provide the following output:</p> <p>60</p> <p>Given code:</p> <pre>1 print(add(40,20)) 2 def add(n1, n2): 3 return n1 + n2</pre> <p>At the moment, the code is faulty and does not provide the requested output! Identify the error(s) and fix the code! Rewrite the code in the free text field.</p>
Correct answer	<p>Change the order and move the print statement to the bottom of the code:</p> <pre>def add(n1, n2): return n1 + n2 print(add(40,20))</pre>
Expected Error(s)	Function is called before the function is defined.

F5C2

Task	<p>The code below should return the following output:</p> <p>Name: Emma Salary: 55000 Name: Ben Salary: 46000</p> <p>Given code:</p> <pre>1 def show_employee(name): 2 print("Name:", name, "Salary:", salary) 3 4 show_employee("Emma", 55000) 5 show_employee("Ben")</pre> <p>At the moment, the code is faulty and does not provide the requested output! Identify the error(s) and fix the code. Don't change the last two lines! Rewrite the code in the free text field.</p>
Correct answer	<p>Add the second parameter for the function and set it to the default value 46000 (line 1):</p> <pre>def show_employee(name, salary=46000):</pre>
Expected Error(s)	No understanding of default parameters.

F1C3

Task	Write a program to create a function that accepts two arguments and calculates addition and subtraction. Additionally, it must return both addition and subtraction in a single return call.
Correct answer	For example: <pre>def calculation(a, b): return addition = a + b return subtraction = a - b res = calculation(40, 10) print(res)</pre>
Expected Error(s)	Multiple, e.g.: not knowing how to define a function; not knowing how to return multiple values (using data structures). Using hardcoded values/overwriting arguments; using wrong operators (+=/-).

F2C3

Task	Write a program to create a function that accepts three numbers and finds the largest number along the three numbers. If you have two numbers that are identical and larger than the third number, print out one of the two numbers. Your code should return the output "Largest number:" plus the actual number. The datatype must not be queried in advance.
Correct answer	<pre>For example: def maximum(a, b, c): if (a >= b) and (a >= c): largest = a elif (b >= a) and (b >= c): largest = b else: largest = c return largest res = maximum(2, 4, 7) print("Largest Number: ", res)</pre>
Expected Error(s)	<p>Multiple, e.g.:</p> <p>not understanding how relational or logical operators work and what type they return or even that they return any value at all. Not understanding how if-statements work, especially that they always take a boolean value to determine if they should be executed.</p> <p>Semantic errors that select the wrong value in some cases.</p> <p>Not knowing how to combine logical expressions or what they mean and how they are interpreted.</p> <p>Accidentally computing the minimum instead.</p>